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JIS **Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)**

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial 2019. November

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) announces its publication of November 2019 issue. Publication of scientific and academic manuscripts in the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) has led towards a wonderful journey. The consistency towards academic contribution has made it possible for the JIS to publish its Volume 3, Issue 2, 2019, in November.

This Volume 3, Issue 2, November 2019, contains research publications from different fields and perspectives contributing to different areas of integrative sciences covering, education, sociology, linguistics, gender studies, psychology, music, etc. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) has incorporated these manuscripts from various interdisciplinary areas into one platform and is available for everyone to download freely.

In this November 2019 issue, JIS has published research articles from various multi-interdisciplinary subjects. JIS is gaining grounds in academia through contribution in interdisciplinary sciences and thus craving towards generating its value by creating an academic value-based community among the reviewers, authors and readers through enriching the beautiful minds towards intelligent minds. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access platform, focusing towards attainment of value-based community within and outside the academic periphery. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) offers free academic services to all authors for submission and publishing and download access to all the interested readers.

Our next Volume 4, issue 1 will be published in May 2020 as scheduled, and we invite scholars from various multi-interdisciplinary disciplines to submit their research and scientific papers.

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
Founder and Editor-in-Chief
Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

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Editorial 2019. November

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